

Application of Artificial Intelligence in Legal Research and Court Practice

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Abstract: This article analyzes the application of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies in legal research and judicial practice. SI plays an important role in the legal field in automating legal documents, predicting court decisions and resolving disputes. These technologies play an important role in speeding up legal processes, increasing efficiency and reducing human errors. However, challenges related to the application of SI, including legal regulation, privacy and security issues, are also highlighted.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, legal research, case law, automation, legal analysis, documents, court forecasting, mediation, privacy, security, legal regulation.

Today, information technology has become an integral part of society, information technology systems that simplify our daily life are increasing more and more. A modern phenomenon such as artificial intelligence (hereinafter referred to as "SI") is also gaining serious importance. The current topic of scientific research, in our opinion, is the analysis of SI technologies, which can be considered as a type of legal technology, its possibilities and difficulties in working with legal documents. The use of SI technologies in working with legal documents requires, first of all, the study of its theoretical and legal aspects. The G20 SI principles of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (2019) are the relevance of their application in legal practice based on sustainable development, welfare, human-oriented values, and the values of the use of SI in legal practice are defined in UNESCO's recommendations on SI ethics (2021), in the "white book" of the European Commission on SI (2020), from the point of view of the need to benefit humanity, the scientific-theoretical research of the feasibility of using SI technologies also expresses the relevance of the subject of the master's thesis.

Also, the necessity of the topic is reflected in our national normative and legal documents, in particular, in Chapter V of the Development Strategy, "Approaching universal problems based on national interests", the 84th goal is to combat corruption with modern information, including information technology. implementation, support for public control and ensuring the development of regulatory legal documents based on the principle of "corruption-free legislation", as well as ensuring timely and complete execution of documents of courts and other bodies, courts priorities such as digitalization of this process by creating an electronic platform that allows sending execution forms electronically without a human factor, creating the possibility to transparently monitor the execution process remotely online were set.

Drafting a constitution is a very complex and controversial process that usually involves lawyers, politicians, and representatives of various sectors of society. Although SI is used in legal studies, contract analysis and other legal fields, its direct involvement in the development of constitutional texts is less common. However, countries with advanced technology sectors and a strong commitment to innovation may be more likely to explore SI programs in future

government processes, including constitutional drafting. Examples of such countries are USA, UK, Canada, Australia and other countries with strong legal and technological infrastructure.

It should be noted that even if SI is used in the development of a constitutional project, it cannot completely replace it, but human experience can complement it. Human considerations, values and legal knowledge remain indispensable in the development of basic documents such as the Constitution. As AI technologies continue to develop, and society's attitude toward the automation of governance evolves, we will likely see experiments like AI-assisted project creation in constitutional processes around the world.

How countries of the world use some methods of using SI in the development of important legal documents; Legal Research: The SI can assist in extensive legal research by analyzing large volumes of legal documents, precedents, and scholarly articles to provide insights and recommendations for constitutional drafting. For example, in the United States, ROSS Intelligence: This SI-based legal research platform analyzes legal documents and processes case law, statutes, and other legal data relevant to lawyers and legal professionals to help them reframe and find solutions to the toughest problems. It is currently widely used in the US legal industry to streamline research processes and improve efficiency.

Language analysis and optimization: SI-based natural language processing (NLP) tools help analyze existing constitutions, identify ambiguities, inconsistencies, and areas for language improvement, and ensure clarity, consistency, and accuracy in structured text.

Public opinion analysis: SI can be used to analyze public opinion, sentiments and feedback collected through surveys, social media and other channels to understand social needs, values and preferences, which can then be used to inform the project. In addition, we may use SI in legislation that is important to another country. For example, it can help with the following features;

Data Analysis and Prediction: SI can analyze large amounts of legal data, including past cases, statutes, and court decisions, to identify trends. This analysis helps legislators anticipate potential legal problems and predict the outcome of proposed legislation. Policy Analysis: SI can help legislators analyze the potential impact of proposed legislation on various stakeholders, sectors, and social groups. By simulating the effects of different policy options, SI can help policymakers make more informed decisions. These examples show how SI technologies can be applied to various aspects of the lawmaking process to improve efficiency, accuracy, and decision-making.

data analysis and prediction, policymakers can better understand the potential impact of legislation, anticipate legal challenges, and make more informed policy decisions.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is one of the technologies that is bringing great changes in various fields today. The legal field is no exception. With the development of artificial intelligence, new approaches are emerging in the field of legal research and judicial practice. SI technologies can play an important role in automating, speeding up and making legal processes more efficient. In this article, we will talk about the ways and benefits of using artificial intelligence in legal research and judicial practice.

1. The role of artificial intelligence in legal research

Legal research is one of the important processes in jurisprudence. Finding relevant laws, analyzing court decisions, and preparing legal documents are time-consuming tasks for lawyers and legal scholars when dealing with legal issues. Artificial intelligence will help speed up these processes.

- **Automated legal search systems** : With the help of SI, it is possible to quickly search for the necessary information among large volumes of legal documents, laws, court decisions and scientific articles. For example, SI programs help lawyers analyze case law decisions and find previously accepted legal principles.

- **Legal Data Analysis** : SI has the ability to automatically analyze legal documents. This technology helps lawyers extract important information from documents and perform legal analysis. At the same time, SI can facilitate data analysis and generate statistical information on legal issues.

2. The role of artificial intelligence in judicial practice

Artificial intelligence allows for simplification and automation of many processes in judicial practice as well. This not only increases the efficiency of the judicial system, but also speeds up the process of considering cases.

- **Automated document analysis and preparation** : Litigation involves a large number of legal documents, including pleadings, judgments and other legal documents, which require a lot of time and resources. With SI, these processes can be automated. Artificial intelligence effectively helps in analyzing documents, structuring them and preparing the necessary documents.
- **Litigation Forecasting** : With the help of SI, it is possible to forecast the outcome of a particular court case. Artificial intelligence takes in large amounts of court decisions and legal data, analyzes the decisions made on various legal issues and makes predictions about the outcome of future legal proceedings. It helps lawyers and judges plan legal strategies.
- **Online Mediation and Dispute Resolution** : SI technologies can be used in online dispute resolution processes outside of court proceedings. Mediation systems based on artificial intelligence automatically analyze disputes between parties and suggest ways to resolve them. This will help reduce the burden on the courts and enable faster resolution of disputes.

3. Advantages of artificial intelligence

- **Efficiency** : SI technologies increase the efficiency of legal research and litigation processes. Lawyers and paralegals will be able to quickly find and analyze data, which will save them time and increase their efficiency.
- **Minimize errors** : Artificial intelligence minimizes errors made by humans. Automating and **analyzing** legal documents will make processes more accurate and reduce the potential for human error.
- **Acceleration of the work process** : SI technologies accelerate the process of preparation and analysis of documents in the court system, which makes the processing of court cases more efficient.
- **Extensive access to data** : In legal research, artificial intelligence enables the study of large amounts of data, which helps lawyers to analyze their research more deeply.

4. Difficulties in the application of SI technologies

The use of artificial intelligence in legal research and judicial practice opens up great prospects, but there are also some difficulties and limitations:

- **Legal regulation** : Appropriate legal regulation is necessary for the application of artificial intelligence in the legal field. In legal practice, questions about the legal status of artificial intelligence, issues of liability and protection of human rights remain open.
- **Balance between technology and human** : No matter how advanced SI technologies are, human judgment and legal reasoning are still important. In the application of artificial intelligence technologies, it is necessary to maintain a balance between the human and the technology.
- **Privacy and Security Issues** : Artificial intelligence processes large amounts of personal and confidential information in the process of analyzing and storing legal documents. This requires special attention to privacy and security issues.

Conclusion. Artificial intelligence technologies can bring about major changes in the fields of legal research and jurisprudence. These technologies help lawyers, judges, and legal professionals conduct legal processes more efficiently and accurately. SI provides great opportunities in preparing documents in legal processes, forecasting court cases and resolving disputes. At the same time, legal regulation, security and human rights issues need to be taken into account for the effective use of artificial intelligence. Maintaining a balance between technology and human thinking is key to the successful use of artificial intelligence in legal practice.

Used literature.

1. Frolova E. E., Ermakova E. P. Utilizing artificial intelligence in legal practice //Smart Technologies for the Digitisation of industry: Entrepreneurial environment. – Singapore : Springer Singapore, 2021. – С. 17-27.
2. Moses L. B. Artificial intelligence in the courts, legal academia and legal practice //AUSTRALIAN LJ. – 2017. – Т. 91. – С. 561.
3. Alarie B., Niblett A., Yoon A. H. How artificial intelligence will affect the practice of law //University of Toronto Law Journal. – 2018. – Т. 68. – №. supplement 1. – С. 106-124.
4. Reiling A. D. Courts and artificial intelligence //IJCA. – 2020. – Т. 11. – С. 1.
5. Biresaw S. M. The impacts of artificial intelligence on research in the legal profession. – 2021.
6. Campbell R. W. Artificial intelligence in the courtroom: The delivery of justice in the age of machine learning //Revista Forumul Judecatorilor. – 2023. – С. 15.
7. Sartor G., Branting L. K. Introduction: judicial applications of artificial intelligence //Judicial applications of artificial intelligence. – Dordrecht : Springer Netherlands, 1998. – С. 1-6.
8. Custers B., Fosch-Villaronga E. (ed.). Law and artificial intelligence: regulating AI and applying AI in legal practice. – Springer Nature, 2022. – Т. 35.
9. Yakubova M. Presentation of the intestinal microbiota as an independent organ. – 2023.
10. Якубова М. М. и др. Оптимизация лечебной тактики у больных с патологической извитостью внутренних сонных артерий //Журнал теоретической и клинической медицины. – 2015. – №. 6. – С. 107-109.
11. Sil R. et al. Artificial intelligence and machine learning based legal application: the state-of-the-art and future research trends //2019 International Conference on Computing, Communication, and Intelligent Systems (ICCCIS). – IEEE, 2019. – С. 57-62.